

AN ANALYSIS OF THE NEUTRALISATION CURVES OF THE COLLOIDAL ACIDS. PART III

By S. L. GUPTA

The neutralisation curves of two colloiddally dispersed resins (resorcinol-formaldehyde resin and Amberlite IR 10) have been analysed theoretically, following the model and the line of analysis described earlier.

In our previous communications (Gupta, Parts I and II, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 587 ; 1957, 34, 63), we suggested a model for the colloidal polybasic acids and also proposed a method for constructing the polybasic acid curve by evaluating a series of dissociation constants and corresponding acid values. It was shown that the titration curve of the polybasic acid of the dimension of colloidal particles could be interpreted as the neutralisation of a series of monobasic acids with drifting dissociation constants. The idea is that at the beginning of a titration, only the strongest and a small fraction of the total intermicellar acidity with a correspondingly high value of the dissociation constant is active, just as in oxalic acid or in phosphoric acid solutions only one-half or one-third respectively of the total acidity is active at the beginning. As this acid is neutralised further dissociation takes place from the surface of the colloidal acid with a corresponding shift in the dissociation constant. In the case of common polybasic acids in true solution, say a dibasic acid of the formula H_2R , the equilibria are

and one gets two dissociation constants for the two types of ions produced, *e.g.*, HR^- and R^{2-} . In the case of the colloidal acids, however, we have assumed that each dissociation from the surface produces an ion R^- , *i.e.*, we are concerned with only one equilibrium, and a number of such ions are just connected together on the surface of the colloidal particles. This happens because contiguous groups are not successively ionised. As the anions, produced from the neutralisation of the strongest fraction, are not different from those produced by the subsequent ionisation, the only observable change is an increase in the total active acidity with a corresponding decrease in the dissociation constant, the curve continuing to remain monobasic. Thus, for colloidal acids containing one type of group, one may expect a series of increasing active acidities with correspondingly diminishing dissociation constants. If the intermicellar groups are themselves dibasic or if the groups are of different types with widely separated dissociation energies, then one may expect two series of such dissociation constants. In that case the titration curve shows a break or an inflection point. In the analysis of the titration curve of the colloidal resorcinol-formaldehyde resin, that follows, one comes across such a situation.

In each of the resorcinol units of the resin structure of the resorcinol-formaldehyde resin there are two -OH groups which are separated from each other by a fixed distance *i.e.*, *meta* to each other in the benzene ring, while the resorcinol units are distributed at random throughout the resin. Consequently the distribution of the -OH groups in a resin particle occurs at random but in pairs and in the case of the titration of this colloidal resin in its H-form, one may expect two series of drifting dissociation constants.

Resorcinol-formaldehyde Resin

The preparation of the acid-catalysed resorcinol-formaldehyde resin, the isolation of the colloidal fraction in its H-form and its titration have been reported earlier (Gupta, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 90). The experimental curve is shown in Fig. 1. The sus-

pension had a colloid content of 0.58 g./litre. As the initial flat run, indicative of ion adsorption, is absent, the acid may be taken to be wholly intermicellar (cf. Case B, Part I, *loc.cit.*). Also preliminary experiments showed that the resin did not adsorb ions unless it was at a very high p_n . In the case of a monobasic acid HR dissociating into H^+ and R^- ions, one gets

$$a_{Na^+} = a_{R^-} + a_{OH^-} - a_{H^+}$$

or

$$b = \frac{Ck}{k+x} + \frac{K_w}{x} - x \quad \dots (1)$$

where 'b', 'C', 'k', 'K_w' and 'x' have their usual significances. Rearranging,

$$Ck = \left(b - \frac{K_w}{x} + x \right) (k+x) \quad \dots (2)$$

By applying this equation to the values obtained by interpolation from the smooth curve and treating the product 'Ck' as constant over short ranges, 'k' can be solved from two consecutive values of 'Ck'. Substitution of the value of 'k' in equation (2) affords the value of 'C'. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

No. of points selected.	$\theta' \times 10^4$.	pH .	Ck (by eq. 2).	k .	pk .	C .
1	2.3 <i>N</i>	5	$2.4 \times 10^{-4} (k+1 \times 10^{-5})$	$6 \times 10^{-6} (k_1)$ from (1) & (2)	5.22	$6.416 \times 10^{-4} (C_1)$
2	5.5	6	$5.5 \times 10^{-4} (k+1 \times 10^{-6})$	$1.2 \times 10^{-5} (k_2)$ from (2) & (3)	5.92	$10.07 \times 10^{-4} (C_2)$
3	9.3	7	$9.5 \times 10^{-4} (k+1 \times 10^{-7})$	$1.89 \times 10^{-7} (k_3)$ from (3) & (4)	6.72	$14.21 \times 10^{-4} (C_3)$
4	13.5	8	$13.5 \times 10^{-4} (k+1 \times 10^{-8})$	$1.54 \times 10^{-8} (k_4)$ from (4) & (5)	7.94	$22.25 \times 10^{-4} (C_4)$
5	21.0	9	$20.9 \times 10^{-4} (k+1 \times 10^{-9})$	$1.95 \times 10^{-9} (k_5)$ from (5) & (6)	8.71	$31.61 \times 10^{-4} (C_5)$
6	27.5	9.5	$27.2 \times 10^{-4} (k+1 \times 10^{-9.5})$	$9.84 \times 10^{-10} (k_6)$ from (6) & (7)	9.01	$36.1 \times 10^{-4} (C_6)$
7	31.0	9.75	$30.44 \times 10^{-4} (k+1 \times 10^{-9.75})$			

It will be seen from the fifth and seventh columns of the table that as the 'C' values increase, the 'k' values diminish. The theoretical curves for the 'C' values with corresponding dissociation constants have been constructed using equation (1) and shown by the dotted lines in Fig. 1. The middle points (approx.) of all such curves joined by the dashed line show the smooth change in pk value throughout the titration up to the first equivalence point, *i.e.*, neutralisation of one -OH group per resorcinol unit. As the experimental values may not be very accurate at the high pH , we have not calculated the values for the second series (pk' series). The maximum neutralisable acidity found is 1220 m.e./100 g. of the oven-dried resin (105°) which is the theoretical value on the assumption that the -OH groups are hydrated with one molecule of water at that temperature (Gupta, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 90).

In our previous analyses for the silicic acid sols and clay systems (Parts I and II, *loc.cit.*), we have indicated these different 'C' and 'k' values by (C_1, k_1), (C_2, k_2) etc., while, in fact, the change from one set of values to the next is continuous. It will be seen from Fig. 1 that the experimental curve passes through those points where a lower value of the active acidity with a higher value of the dissociation constant tends to deflect the curve to the right, while a higher value of the active acidity with a lower value of the dissociation constant tends to deflect the curve to the left of the experimental curve. The experimental curve represents the mean course and is necessarily so for a continuous change in active acidity and dissociation constant. The oscillations will vanish by selecting closer points for evaluation.

Amberlite IR 100 *

The resin was wet-ground in an agate mortar and the fine fraction remaining above a height of 10 cm after 8 hours of undisturbed settling was syphoned off and collected

* This resin was obtained by the courtesy of Messrs. Rohm and Haas Company, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, U. S. A., through Dr. S. K. Mukherjee, Reader in Applied Chemistry, Calcutta University, for experimental purposes.

in $N/20$ -HCl medium. This was then filtered through a sintered glass crucible, washed free from HCl and resuspended in double distilled water. The colloid content was determined (1.98 g./litre) by drying at $105-10^{\circ}$. The neutralisation curve obtained is shown in Fig. 2.

In Amberlite IR 100, one gets an entirely different picture. The resin adsorbs ions and consequently the total acidity is partly micellar and partly intermicellar (cf. Case C, in Part I, *loc. cit.*), i.e., $C_a + C_f$. The intermicellar groups are again of two types i.e., the $-\text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups and the phenolic $-\text{OH}$ groups (Kunin and Myers, "Ion Exchange Resins", 1950, p. 58), i.e., $C_f = (C-\text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H})_f + (C-\text{OH})_f$. The intermicellar $-\text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups being strongly ionisable are completely ionised and behave as any soluble strong acid and are the first to be neutralised simultaneously with ion adsorption, while the intermicellar phenolic $-\text{OH}$ groups being weakly ionisable are neutralised subsequently as a polybasic acid, being represented by a series of monobasic acids, $C_1, C_2 \dots C_n$ with drifting dissociation constants, $k_1, k_2 \dots k_n$, such that $C_n = (C-\text{OH})_f$. Consequently, the initial stretch is given by

$$b = C_a + (C-\text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H})_f + \frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} + \frac{K_w}{x} - \frac{x \cdot C_a}{(C-\text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H})_f + \frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} + \frac{K_w}{x}} - x \quad (3)$$

and by

$$b = C_a + (C-\text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H})_f + \frac{C_2 k_2}{k_2 + x} + \frac{K_w}{x} - x \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

etc. for subsequent stretches.

The analysis has been made in the following lines. The initial p_H gives the value of $(C-\text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H})_f$ as due to the presence of these strongly ionisable groups on the surface of the resin particles the dissociation of the phenolic $-\text{OH}$ groups, $(C-\text{OH})_f$, remain almost suppressed. The initial p_H recorded is 3.8, and consequently, we have assumed $(C-\text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H})_f$ to have a value of $1.58 \times 10^{-4}N$. The final inflection signifying the end of titration is not very sharp and therefore there may be some uncertainty about the actual value of $(C-\text{OH})_f$, but the phenolic slope to the right of the line AB is unmistakable. The micellar acidity, C_a , calculated over the whole suspension is evaluated at $30.92 \times 10^{-4}N$.

As in resorcinol-formaldehyde resin, we have calculated the different C and k values from the slope of the curve to the right of the line AB, which are given below in Table II. The final value, i.e., C_n has been taken to be equal to $(C-\text{OH})_f$.

TABLE II

$C \dots$	$3.86 \times 10^{-4}(C_1)$	$4.28 \times 10^{-4}(C_2)$	$5.14 \times 10^{-4}(C_3)$	$6.84 \times 10^{-4}(C_4)$	$11.0 \times 10^{-4}(C_5)$
$k \dots$	$1.84 \times 10^{-6}(k_1)$	$1.40 \times 10^{-6}(k_2)$	$3.50 \times 10^{-7}(k_3)$	$2.71 \times 10^{-8}(k_4)$	$1.00 \times 10^{-9}(k_5)$

Thus assuming any value of 'x', the corresponding 'b' value can be obtained by using equations (3) and (4). The theoretical curve, PMQN, is shown in Fig. 2., and the results of analysis are shown in Table III. Also $(\alpha_{x_n})_f$ at any p_H is given by

$$(a_{\text{Na}^+})_I = (C - \text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H})_I + \frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} + \frac{K_w}{x} - x \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

for the initial stretch and replacing (C_1, k_1) by C_2, k_2 etc. for other stretches.

TABLE III

p_H	3.8	4.0	5.0	5.5	6.5	7.5	8.5	9.5
$b \times 10^4$	0.0	12.82	31.59	33.56	36.0	37.22	38.64	41.62
$(a_{\text{Na}^+})_f \times 10^4$	0.0	0.65	2.08	2.97	5.08	6.30	7.72	10.70
$(a_{\text{Na}^+})_x \times 10^4$	0.0	12.17	29.51	30.59	30.92	30.92	30.92	30.92
		$C_1 k_1$			$C_2 k_2$	$C_3 k_3$	$C_4 k_4$	$C_5 k_5$

It will be seen that the curves are nearly coincident. The slight discrepancy may be due either to non-attainment of equilibrium or to ion specificity that is frequently observed in these systems. The curve PQR shows approximately what the curve could have been if the phenolic $-\text{OH}$ groups were not present in the resin system and the intercellular acidity were made up of only methylenesulphonic acid groups.

FIG. 2

The figure also shows a plot of $(a_{\text{Na}^+})_I$ against 'b', i. e., C_{NaOH} . The experimental curves for p_H and a_{Na^+} obtained by Marshall and Upchurch (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1953, 57, 618) in the case of the titration of Amberlite IR 120, a nuclear sulphonic acid resin, strongly resemble these curves except for the fact that the p_H curve of Amberlite IR 120 appears to be one unit lower. If the p_H curve is raised by slightly more than one unit of p_H , as a whole, then it will fit completely with our method of calculation. That

the p_n curve is to be raised can be shown from the fact that at $p_n = 3$ ($a_n^+ = 1 \times 10^{-3} N$), $a_{K^+} = 0$ and at about $p_n = 4$ ($a_n^+ = 1 \times 10^{-4} N$), the $a_{K^+} \cong 0.5 \times 10^{-4} N$ as observed from the curves; consequently with the disappearance of 9×10^{-4} equivalents of H^+ ions we are getting only 0.5×10^{-4} equivalent of K^+ ions in the intermicellar solution. For the neutralisation of any acidic suspension, weak or strong, the concentration of the cation of the added base will always exceed or at least be approximately equal to the H^+ ions disappearing from the solution, and this can only happen by raising the p_n curve as a whole.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA

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AN ANALYSIS OF THE NEUTRALISATION CURVES OF THE COLLOIDAL ACIDS. PART IV

BY S. L. GUPTA

The features of the conductometric titration curves of the colloidal acids have been discussed with reference to our previous theoretical findings on the features of the potentiometric titration curves. The changes such titration curves undergo, when a diacidic base is used for titrating the colloidal acid instead of a monoacidic base, have been brought out. An attempt has also been made to show the extent of agreement between our method of calculation and some published experimental informations on the neutralisation of colloidal AgI sols with hydrogen as the counter-ions.

Conductometric Titration Curves.—The nature of the potentiometric titration curves of the colloidal acids has already been analysed in detail (Gupta, this *Journal*, 1956, **33**, 587; 1957, **34**, 63). The assumptions involved in the deduction of the equations representing potentiometric titration curves of particular shapes necessarily and simultaneously fix up conductometric titration curves of definite and corresponding patterns. It has been assumed that only the free ions and the colloidal particles are the carriers of electricity and the adsorbed ions do not contribute to the conductivity under normal field strength used in the conductivity measurements. Under such circumstances, the expected nature of the specific conductivity-concentration curves will be exhibited by curves A' , B' and C' , corresponding to potentiometric curves A , B and C in Fig. 1., and by A' and B' to those corresponding to A and B in Fig. 2, respectively. A brief description of the theoretical curves shown in Figs. 1 and 2 is given below.